

score

D9.10-SCORE Second International Workshop

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
ATU	Atlantic Technological University
CCLs	Coastal City Living Labs
DIY	Do-It-Yourself
EBA	Ecosystem-Based Adaptation
EU	European Union
EUWRC	European Week of Regions and Cities
IoT	Internet of Things
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
RPOs	Research Performing Organizations
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
SCORE	Smart Technologies and Community Engagement for Climate Resilience
HWL	High Water Line
LWL	Low Water Line
RCP	Representative Concentration Pathway
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification

BACKGROUND: ABOUT THE SCORE PROJECT

SCORE is a four-year EU-funded project aiming to increase climate resilience in European coastal cities.

The intensification of extreme weather events, coastal erosion and sea-level rise are major challenges to be urgently addressed by European coastal cities. The science behind these disruptive phenomena is complex, and advancing climate resilience requires progress in data acquisition, forecasting, and understanding of the potential risks and impacts for real-scenario interventions. The Ecosystem-Based Approach (EBA) supported by smart technologies has potential to increase climate resilience of European coastal cities; however, it is not yet adequately understood and coordinated at European level.

SCORE outlines a co-creation strategy, developed via a network of 10 coastal city 'Living Labs' (CCLs), to rapidly, equitably and sustainably enhance coastal city climate resilience through EBAs and sophisticated digital technologies.

The 10 coastal city Living Labs involved in the project are: Sligo and Dublin, Ireland; Barcelona/Vilanova i la Geltrú, Benidorm and Basque Country, Spain; Oeiras, Portugal; Massa, Italy; Piran, Slovenia; Gdansk, Poland; Samsun, Turkey.

SCORE will establish an integrated coastal zone management framework for strengthening EBA and smart coastal city policies, creating European leadership in coastal city climate change adaptation in line with The Paris Agreement. It will provide innovative platforms to empower stakeholders' deployment of EBAs to increase climate resilience, business opportunities and financial sustainability of coastal cities.

The SCORE interdisciplinary team consists of 28 world-leading organisations from academia, local authorities, RPOs, and SMEs encompassing a wide range of skills including environmental science and policy, climate modelling, citizen and social science, data management, coastal management and engineering, security and technological aspects of smart sensing research.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the SCORE project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003534. Although the aim of this document was to report on the 2nd SCORE International Workshop, the deliverable is actually reporting on the organization of two distinct workshops, which were organized by SCORE partners at the end of 2024: a workshop in the framework of the European Coastal Challenge Summit - Littoral24 (24–27 September 2024, Constanta, Romania) and a panel session at the European Week of Regions and Cities – EUWRC (7–10 October 2024, Brussels, Belgium).

The reasons for participating in both events were the different focus and the different target audiences at these events:

- The conference themes of the **European Coastal Challenge Summit** were highly linked to SCORE activities (climate change adaptation strategies; coastal and marine protected areas and ecosystem services assessment; challenging conditions and transformations for coastal communities during current crises; perspectives in support of Sustainable Blue Economy through participatory approaches and engagement with the stakeholders; improving coastal and maritime governance and cross-sectoral collaboration) with its target audience including experts and the Young Professionals Coastal Community from 14 Member States, the UK and Brasil as a critical platform for discussing strategies that balance ecological preservation, coastal communities and economic sustainability.
- The **European Week of Regions and Cities** is an annual event aiming to discuss common challenges for Europe's regions and cities and examine possible solutions by bringing together politicians, decision-makers, experts and practitioners of cohesion policy, as well as stakeholders from business, banking, civil society organisations, academia, the EU institutions and the media. It is an excellent platform for capacity-building, learning and exchange of experience and good practice to facilitate cooperation and networking between regions and cities. Our reason for being there was to raise awareness of SCORE activities and solutions implemented in our CCLs, to showcase communities' contributions to regional development goals for climate-resilient regions and see how this could be of interest to other cities and regions.

The SCORE workshop organized at the Littoral24 conference was focused on the theme “Smart Technologies and Community Engagement with EBA for Climate Resilience Actions,” providing a forum for academic researchers, policymakers, and practitioners to explore cutting-edge approaches to coastal resilience.

The SCORE panel session at the EUWRC was titled “Empowering Communities: Smart Tech & Citizen Science for Sustainable Futures”, exploring how smart technologies and citizen science can empower communities to address local sustainability challenges and contribute to regional development goals.

In both events we were also present with a SCORE exhibition booth showcasing the project's tools, methodologies, and key achievements, facilitating networking with conference attendees.

All in all, the SCORE participation in Littoral24 and EUWRC was a success, with several new contacts established, and project material distributed among several stakeholders. These events underscore SCORE's role in advancing community-driven climate resilience through interdisciplinary collaboration and innovative solutions.

LINKS WITH OTHER PROJECT ACTIVITIES

This deliverable is part of the Work Package 9 (WP9: Dissemination, communication, exploitation) which is a transversal work package integrating the results of all the WPs for the dissemination, communication, and exploitation process: it will ensure that the outputs and learnings arising from all the activities of the project are visible to a wider audience, can be learned from and implemented on a European scale.

The workshops reported in this deliverable contributed to promote project outcomes as part of the following WPs:

- WP2 (Coastal City Living Labs Design, Implementation, and Evaluation on the Coastal City Living Labs), which focuses on developing a novel Coastal City Living Lab (CCLL) framework for the deployment, evaluation, and uptake of integrated Ecosystem-Based Approaches (EBA) and smart technologies across European coastal cities.
- WP4 (CCLL co-warning and co-monitoring) focused on citizen science and empowering local communities, also through the use of low-cost sensors.
- WP8 (Development of integrated early warning support and spatial digital twin solution prototypes) aiming to develop a GIS Based Early Warning Support System and Digital Twin platform.

TABLE OF CONTENT

1. Introduction	9
2. Setting and agenda	9
2.1. Setting and Agenda for the Workshop at Littoral24	9
2.2. Setting and Agenda for the Workshop at European Week of Regions and Cities (EUWRC)	10
3. SCORE scientific advanceMents: Smart technologies and citizen science for climate resilience	11
3.1. Littoral24: Smart Technologies and Community Engagement with EBA for Climate Resilience	12
3.1.1. Advancing community-driven climate resilience through smart integrated systematic co-creation methodologies	12
3.1.2. The Changing Statistics of Storm Surges in NW Ireland	13
3.1.3. Advancing community-driven climate resilience through smart integrated systematic co-creation methodologies	13
3.1.4. Citizen science in coastal erosion monitoring – Smart pebbles in Sligo, Ireland	13
3.1.5. Analysing the role of Ecosystem-based Adaptation to build coastal resilience in European Living Labs	14
3.2. EUWRC 2024: Empowering Communities: Smart Tech & Citizen Science for Sustainable Futures	14
3.2.1. Academia: Smart Technologies & Citizen Science	15
3.2.2. Private Organization: Digital Twin and Early Warning Support System	15
3.2.3. Public Institutions & Citizens: DIY Smart Technologies and Community Engagement	15
4. Event promotion	16
4.1. SCORE Website	16

4.2. SCORE Social Media	16
4.3. SCORE newsletter & mailing	17
4.4. Others	18
5. Participants	18
6. Conclusion.....	18

INDEX OF FIGURES

Figure 1: The SCORE Project Coordinator, Salem Gharbia, presenting SCORE at the introductory session of the Littoral24	12
Figure 2: The EUWRC workshop: SCORE Panellists and moderator (Ester Toledo, Iolanda Sanchez Alcaraz, Salem Gharbia, Iulia Anton and Giovanni Serafino) discussing the SCORE Project achievements and importance of smart technologies for climate resilience.....	15
Figure 3: Social media promotions on SCORE	17
Figure 4: Mail about the SCORE event sent to all subscribers	18

INDEX OF TABLES

Table 1: SCORE international Littoral24 workshop agenda	10
Table 2: SCORE international workshop EUWRC agenda.....	11

1. INTRODUCTION

The workshop held at the Littoral 2024 "European Coastal Challenge Summit" on September 24, 2024, in Constanta, Romania, provided a key platform for SCORE to engage with the European coastal and maritime community. Hosted by Ovidius University of Constanta, this conference gathered experts from across Europe to discuss strategies for sustainable coastal management, climate resilience, and the challenges facing coastal communities. The workshop brought together SCORE experts from ATU Sligo, UCD, SCC and ENT facilitating discussions on smart technologies, ecosystem-based adaptation (EBA), and community-driven initiatives, reinforcing the project's commitment to collaborative innovation in addressing coastal climate change impacts.

Following the Littoral24 conference, SCORE participated in the European Week of Regions and Cities (EUWRC) to present the work on regional sustainability and climate resilience to a broader European audience. The EUWRC panel session, titled "Empowering Communities: Smart Tech & Citizen Science for Sustainable Futures," was held on October 10, 2024, from 9:30 to 10:30 CET at the Albert Borschette Congress Center, Brussels. This session focused on the role of smart technologies and citizen science in fostering community engagement for sustainable development. It brought together experts from ATU Sligo, MBI srl, and the City Council of Vilanova to discuss how affordable smart tech can enable collaboration across stakeholders to address local challenges related to sustainable cities, greening initiatives, and climate resilience. The session demonstrated the value of digital tools and citizen science in empowering communities to contribute effectively to regional development goals. Participants also had the opportunity to interact with SCORE's booth, showcasing tools like the low-cost sensors catalogue and co-creation toolkit, further enhancing the engagement and dissemination of project outcomes.

2. SETTING AND AGENDA

2.1. Setting and Agenda for the Workshop at Littoral24

The SCORE workshop at the Littoral 2024 "European Coastal Challenge Summit" was designed to provide a platform for sharing experiences and discussing challenges related to coastal climate resilience and adaptation. The SCORE International Workshop at Littoral24 featured two thematic sessions. The first session focused on "Living Lab Experiences and Innovations to Tackle Climate Change," showcasing case studies and research on low-cost monitoring technologies, ecosystem-based adaptation, citizen science, and co-creation methodologies. The second session, "Stakeholder Engagement and Social Initiatives," highlighted the importance of collaboration and community-driven efforts in building social and climate resilience. Each session also included panel discussions, a Q&A session, and networking opportunities among participants. The agenda was designed to facilitate knowledge exchange, foster collaboration, and inspire further action in the realm of coastal resilience and sustainability.

Table 1: SCORE international Littoral24 workshop agenda

SCORE international Littoral24 workshop agenda	
LL Experiences and Innovations to Tackle Climate Change	
12:00 – 12:30	Khurram Riaz, Marion McAfee, Salem Gharbia (ATU, Ireland) Low-cost remote sensing approaches for coastal erosion monitoring and prediction in Northwest of Ireland
12:30 – 01:00	Tasneem Ahmed (ATU, Ireland), Andrea Cucco (CNR, Italy), Giovanni Quattrocchi (CNR, Italy) The changing statistics of storm surges in Northwest of Ireland
09:20 – 09:30	Salem Gharbia (ATU, Ireland) Advancing community-driven climate resilience through smart integrated systematic co-creation methodologies
P09:30 – 09:40	Iulia Anton, Salem Gharbia (ATU, Ireland), Chiara Cocco (UCD, Ireland), Alessandro Pozzebon (UNIFI, Italy), Duccio Bertoni (UNIFI, Italy), Pete Murtagh (SCC, Ireland) Citizen science in coastal erosion monitoring – Smart Pebbles in Sligo, Ireland
09:40 – 10:00	Ananya Tiwari, Salem Gharbia (ATU, Ireland), Luis Campos Rodrigues (ENT, Spain) Analysing the Role of Ecosystem-Based Adaptation to build Coastal Resilience in European Living Labs
10:00 – 10:30	Panel discussion: Living Lab experiences and Innovations to tackle climate change
10:30 – 11:00	Coffee break & Networking session
Stakeholder Engagement and Social Initiatives	
13:30 – 13:50	Panel discussion: Stakeholder engagement and Social Initiatives
13:50 – 14:00	Q&A with Closing remarks

2.2. Setting and Agenda for the Workshop at European Week of Regions and Cities (EUWRC)

The SCORE panel session at the European Week of Regions and Cities (EUWRC) aimed to empower communities using smart technologies and citizen science to address local sustainability and climate resilience challenges. The workshop provided a platform for SCORE partners from ATU Sligo, MBI srl, and the City Council of Vilanova i la Geltrú, representing the quadruple helix of citizens, policymakers, academia, and private organizations, to discuss how they are integrating affordable smart tech with various stakeholders to foster regional development goals. The panel session titled “Empowering Communities: Smart Tech & Citizen Science for Sustainable Futures,” was held on October 10, 2024, from 9:30 to 10:30 CET at the Albert Borschette Congress Center, Room AB-4A. The session was structured around presentations from SCORE partners on how citizen science and digital tools can enhance community engagement, followed by a 20-minute panel discussion and a 10-minute Q&A session. This allowed participants to delve deeper into the methodologies and outcomes of community-driven initiatives, sharing lessons learned and exploring collaborative solutions for a sustainable future. The session was an opportunity to showcase the SCORE project’s tools and solutions, including the low-cost sensors catalogue, co-creation toolkit, and digital twin, designed to improve climate monitoring, projections, and knowledge sharing among communities.

Table 2: SCORE international workshop EUWRC agenda

SCORE international workshop EUWRC agenda	
Expert panel discussion on 'Smart Tech & Citizen Science for Sustainable Futures'	
09:30 – 09:35	Introduction: Iulia Anton (moderator) introduced the SCORE project and its contribution in fostering sustainable futures through smart technology and citizen science. She highlighted key achievements from the project such as the deployment of affordable tech solutions, community engagement strategies, and the role of the quadruple helix (citizens, policymakers, academia, and private organizations) in driving regional development goals related to climate resilience.
09:36 – 10:08	<p>Academia: Smart Technologies & Citizen Science Dr Salem Gharbia, Head of the Department of Environmental Science at Atlantic Technologic University from Sligo, Ireland and the project coordinator of the SCORE Project. Dr Gharbia provided insights from an academic perspective.</p> <p>Public Institutions & Citizens: DIY Smart Technologies and Community Engagement </p> <p>Iolanda Sanchez Alcaraz, a councillor at the City Council of Villanova I la Geltru together with Ester Toledo a representative from the same institution. The City Council of Villanova I la Geltru is one of the partners of the SCORE project and the representatives of the Villanova CCLL. Both of them talked from the city council perspective, specifically with policy and citizen engagement.</p> <p>Private Organization: Digital Twin and Early Warning Support System Giovanni Serafino, Project Manager at MBI (SCORE partner). He is working with the SCORE team to develop the EWSS and the DT for a few CCLLs from the project. Mr Serafino represented the private sector and shared insights about their role in this project, particularly about the DT and EWSS systems.</p>
10:09 – 10:23	Audience interaction and Q&A session with the panellists on smart technologies, Early warning system (EWS), citizen science activities, low-cost sensors and how they will help the coastal communities.
10:24 – 10:28	Audience poll and feedback for the session
10:29 – 10:30	End

Additionally, an exhibition booth was successfully set up to showcase the achievements and innovations of the project. The exhibition booth was open throughout the duration of the EUWRC event, and it was manned by several project partners from Euronovia, ERINN and ATU. Key materials such as policy briefs, EBA postcards, MOOC postcards, brochures, and sign-up sheets were showcased and presented to visitors at the booth. Additional content, including videos and slides presenting each CCLL as well as the main results of the projects were displayed at the booth (Provided in Appendix 1 and Appendix 2).

3. SCORE SCIENTIFIC ADVANCEMENTS: SMART TECHNOLOGIES AND CITIZEN SCIENCE FOR CLIMATE RESILIENCE

The SCORE project stands at the forefront of integrating cutting-edge technologies with community-driven approaches to enhance climate resilience. Through Littoral24 and EUWRC 2024, participants explored the application of smart technologies such as digital twins and low-cost sensors, in monitoring and predicting coastal dynamics and storm surge impacts. These advancements not only provide accurate data for real-time decision-making but also empower local communities to actively engage in climate adaptation efforts. They further explored how community

involvement is crucial for preparedness, emphasizing that the integration of smart technologies with citizen science enables communities to actively participate in climate resilience efforts. By combining these tools with citizen science initiatives, SCORE exemplifies the power of community collaboration in driving effective and sustainable solutions to environmental challenges.

3.1. Littoral24: Smart Technologies and Community Engagement with EBA for Climate Resilience

Figure 1: The SCORE Project Coordinator, Salem Gharbia, presenting SCORE at the introductory session of the Littoral24

3.1.1. Advancing community-driven climate resilience through smart integrated systematic co-creation methodologies

The presentation showcased case studies from the SCORE project, emphasizing the application of remote sensing techniques to monitor coastal erosion in the Northwest of Ireland. A novel automatic shoreline detection methodology was employed to analyse 25 years of data, incorporating high waterline (HWL) and low waterline (LWL) indicators to identify high erosion hotspot transects. By focusing on the seasonal and annual distribution of extreme waterlines, the presentation effectively highlighted erosion severity and shoreline dynamics across three dissipative beaches of Sligo. Key findings demonstrated the stabilisation of extreme waterline events at certain sites, while others exhibited dynamic behaviour, particularly in areas with distinct morphologies and narrower foreshores. This approach enhances the understanding of coastal processes and provides actionable insights for improving community-driven resilience to coastal erosion. This work is mainly conducted through WP4, WP7.

3.1.2. The Changing Statistics of Storm Surges in NW Ireland

The presentation highlighted one of the case studies from the SCORE project, focusing on storm surge projections for Donegal Bay in northwest Ireland. The study employed the SHYFEM hydrodynamic model¹ and associated sub-models to analyze storm surge dynamics, tide interactions, and the impacts of mean sea-level rise.

This case study analysis revealed that non-linear tide-surge interactions were negligible, allowing tides, storm surges, and mean sea-level rise to be combined linearly in projections. Long-term projections (2045-2094) under RCP² 8.5 showed consistently higher storm surge magnitudes compared to RCP 4.5, while rising total water levels were driven primarily by mean sea-level rise rather than changes in storm surge intensity. Additionally, tidal dynamics in the region were found to be stable over 177 years, with only minor changes in amplitude and phase. This work is mainly conducted through WP3.

3.1.3. Advancing community-driven climate resilience through smart integrated systematic co-creation methodologies

The principal investigator for the SCORE project outlined the overarching goals of the SCORE project. The presentation covered a wide range of topics relevant to the SCORE project, focusing on the integration of Nature-Based Solutions (NBSs) and smart technologies to address societal challenges. It began by emphasizing the role of Living Labs as a co-creation process, which enables stakeholders to collaboratively develop and test innovative solutions in real-life settings. The importance of low-cost sensing technologies was discussed, highlighting their role in monitoring environmental changes and gathering data for accurate, real-time analysis. Integrated data modeling and processing were presented as essential tools for what-if scenario modeling, allowing stakeholders to explore different scenarios and assess risks effectively. The discussion also covered the roles of frontrunners and followers within the CCLs, ensuring coordination and collaboration among participants. Connections between various models, such as Digital Twin and Digital Shadow, were emphasized to provide comprehensive insights and support informed decision-making. The structure of the Early-Warning Support Module (EWS) was presented, underscoring its role in providing timely alerts and preparedness for environmental risks. Several case studies were highlighted, including Vilanova fluvial floods, Sligo Shoreline movement through low-cost sensors, and scenarios predicting a 2-meter rise in sea level. This work is mainly conducted through WP4 and WP8.

3.1.4. Citizen science in coastal erosion monitoring – Smart pebbles in Sligo, Ireland

This case study focused on Raghly Beach, located on the Raghly Peninsula in County Sligo, Ireland. This dynamic coastal environment is characterized by a combination of rocky outcrops, pebbles, and sandy stretches, shaped by strong Atlantic currents and winds. The natural processes of sediment transport driven by tides and wave energy have resulted in gradual erosion, reshaping the beach and impacting local ecosystems.

The study employed Smart Pebbles—specially designed with RFID transponders—to monitor sediment movement, offering insights into erosion and deposition patterns. Community involvement played a key role, with volunteers trained to deploy the pebbles, retrieve them using RFID readers, and log data. Over two months, 106 pebbles were deployed, and 22 were recovered, allowing for detailed tracking of sediment dynamics.

¹ SHYFEM (Shallow water HYdrodynamic Finite Element Model) is a numerical model used to simulate water circulation in coastal and estuarine environments. For further details, refer to the relevant SCORE Deliverable, which is publicly available.

² RCP (Representative Concentration Pathway): A greenhouse gas concentration trajectory adopted by the IPCC, representing different climate futures based on varying levels of emissions.

The results revealed clear patterns in sediment transport and coastal processes. Most pebbles moved inland toward the shore due to tidal forces and wave action, with certain pebbles, such as 18 and 6, showing longer displacements influenced by stronger currents. Conversely, some pebbles, such as 14, displayed minimal movement, indicating weaker wave activity or resistance due to their size or position. Clusters of pebbles moved in consistent patterns within specific areas of the beach, reflecting localized wave or tidal influences. Despite some changes in the volume of pebbles, their weight remained largely unchanged, suggesting surface erosion occurred without significant material loss. This study underscored the dynamic nature of hydrodynamic forces influencing beach formation and emphasized the importance of investigating sediment transport and coastal processes. Additionally, the case study highlighted the value of citizen science initiatives in empowering local communities and fostering greater awareness of their surrounding environments. This work is conducted through work package 4.

3.1.5. Analysing the role of Ecosystem-based Adaptation to build coastal resilience in European Living Labs

This presentation explored the role of Ecosystem-based Adaptation (EBA) in building climate resilience across the CCLs. The focus was on analyzing different multi-criteria approaches to assess the effectiveness of EBA strategies in managing climate change-related hazards such as coastal flooding, inland flooding, and heatwaves. By prioritizing predefined EBA options—such as green spaces, tree planting, and riparian reforestation in Oarsoaldea, Spain, or historic wells and sustainable pavements in Piran, Slovenia—the study was able to identify the social, environmental, and economic co-benefits of these strategies. This approach highlighted the importance of locally tailored solutions for flood risk reduction and the value of integrating ecosystem services into decision-making processes. For example, in Sligo, Ireland, afforestation, peatland restoration, and wetland restoration were identified as critical for reducing coastal flooding, emphasizing their role in carbon capture and recreation.

The workshop also underscored the significance of community involvement, using different tools to monitor coastal processes, which not only empowers local communities but also enhances the accuracy of flood risk assessments. This presentation highlighted the importance of combining scientific analysis with community engagement to create effective and sustainable adaptation solutions for coastal cities facing the challenges of climate change. This work is mainly conducted through WP5 and WP7.

3.2. EUWRC 2024: Empowering Communities: Smart Tech & Citizen Science for Sustainable Futures

This workshop session started by emphasizing the importance of integrating community engagement with smart technologies to address local sustainability challenges. The moderator Iulia Anton, Project manager for SCORE set the stage by explaining how the SCORE project serves as a bridge between local communities and scientific advancements, fostering collaboration across the quadruple helix—citizens, policymakers, academia, and private organizations. The panel members began discussing the significance of the SCORE project by highlighting various aspects from SCORE.

Figure 2: The EUWRC workshop: SCORE Panellists and moderator (Ester Toledo, Iolanda Sanchez Alcaraz, Salem Gharbia, Iulia Anton and Giovanni Serafino) discussing the SCORE Project achievements and importance of smart technologies for climate resilience

3.2.1. Academia: Smart Technologies & Citizen Science

This session discussed the role of smart technologies in citizen science projects, particularly in the context of climate resilience through the academia perspective. Project Coordinator Salem Gharbia from ATU highlighted how tools such as digital twins and predictive modeling are used to simulate various scenarios, allowing communities to understand the impact of different interventions on local ecosystems. Also explained the benefits of using affordable tech for data collection and analysis, emphasizing its importance in enabling real-time monitoring and feedback. The session highlighted a case study where a smart technology platform was used to track sediment movements in Sligo, Ireland, providing valuable insights into coastal erosion patterns and informing mitigation strategies.

3.2.2. Private Organization: Digital Twin and Early Warning Support System

Giovanni Serafino from MBI discussed the use of digital twin technology and early warning systems to enhance community resilience against climate-related hazards. He explained how these tools combine data from various sources—satellites, IoT sensors, and citizen science initiatives—to create predictive models that help in disaster preparedness and response. The Digital Twin allows for a detailed, virtual representation of real-world systems, enabling better forecasting of extreme weather events and subsequent proactive measures by local authorities.

3.2.3. Public Institutions & Citizens: DIY Smart Technologies and Community Engagement

Iolanda Sanchez Alcaraz, Councilor of Vilanova i la Geltrú (Spain), and Ester Toledo Arroyo Tècnica de Medi Ambient, Regidoria de Medi Ambient from the city, focused on the role of DIY smart technologies and community engagement in fostering climate resilience. They discussed how public institutions can support local councils in facilitating access to affordable tech solutions. The speaker emphasized the importance of co-creation processes, where communities contribute their knowledge and ideas, to ensure that the solutions are tailored to local needs. Several projects were highlighted where citizens used DIY smart technologies to monitor local conditions—such as water quality in lakes and air quality in neighborhoods—and how this data was used to inform policy decisions. The speaker stressed the need for equitable benefit sharing and transparent impact assessments to ensure that projects do not disproportionately affect vulnerable groups and that the benefits are widely accessible.

Following the individual presentations, the panel, moderated by Iulia Anton from ATU, engaged in a discussion on how smart technologies can bridge the gap between local communities and scientific advancements to enable collaborative problem-solving. It was followed by a Q&A session open to all participants.

Throughout the session, a poll was conducted on the Slido platform to further engage the participants. The speakers addressed the answers provided by the participants during the discussions.

4. EVENT PROMOTION

The promotion of the SCORE workshops was done through both the event websites and the SCORE communication channels. The European Week of Regions and Cities had a dedicated website with webpage for each session (both the SCORE workshop and the exhibition stand). The SCORE team was responsible for updating the information on these pages and registration was done through the EWRC website. Through the SCORE channels (website, newsletter, social media), Euronovia increased the visibility of the event to its community.

4.1. SCORE Website

The SCORE workshop at Littoral24 and the panel session at the EUWRC were announced in news articles on the SCORE website with the relevant information and registration links:

- <https://score-eu-project.eu/2024/07/04/score-workshop-at-the-littoral24-conference/>
- <https://score-eu-project.eu/2024/07/04/score-at-the-european-week-of-regions-and-cities/>

A summary article of the panel session at EUWRC was also published at the end of the event: <https://score-eu-project.eu/2024/10/11/a-look-back-at-the-scores-participation-in-the-european-week-of-regions-and-cities/>

4.2. SCORE Social Media

The workshops and booths were actively promoted on social media with several dedicated posts starting in July 2024, when the registrations officially opened.

Figure 3: Social media promotions on SCORE

4.3. SCORE newsletter & mailing

The events were also promoted through the SCORE sixth newsletter sent in July 2024 to 568 subscribers: <https://score-eu-project.eu/2024/07/09/score-sixth-newsletter-july-2024/>.

A dedicated mailing was also sent out to the same subscribers list on 9 September 2024 to further promote the EUWRC event and encourage registration, since having enough registrations was a condition from the organisers for the session to be maintained.

Figure 4: Mail about the SCORE event sent to all subscribers

4.4. Others

During the SCORE workshop events, for the promotions, we utilized flyers, roll-up banners, and posters to engage participants and convey key messages effectively. These promotional tools were displayed on the stands throughout the duration of the workshop events.

5. PARTICIPANTS

The SCORE workshop at Littoral 24 saw a total of 105 registered participants, while the number of registered participants for the SCORE workshop at the EWRC reached **101 people**. The registered participants for these workshops were from various organisations (Academia/Research Institutes, Private sector, Local and Regional Authorities, EU-funded projects, Associations and NGOs, National administrations, EU institutions) and countries (within and outside Europe). Additional people were reached through the booths, where SCORE partners could interact with participants during the whole event duration.

6. CONCLUSION

Both Littoral24 and EUWRC were successful in achieving their objectives, each providing valuable insights to the respective target audiences.

Littoral24 successfully delved into the technical aspects of coastal and marine management, with a strong emphasis on smart technologies, storm-surge models, and innovative solutions. Through detailed case studies and empirical results, participants explored the latest advancements and their applications in real-world scenarios. The event provided a platform for sharing knowledge, exchanging ideas, and fostering collaboration among technical experts, paving the way for further development in this field.

The EUWRC workshop focused on the broader scope of different tools and resources management, emphasizing the importance of involving all stakeholders. The conference highlighted the role of the quadruple helix - government, industry, academia, and civil society - in decision-making processes. By integrating the perspectives of all these groups, participants discussed strategies to enhance collaboration, promote sustainability, and address the multifaceted challenges of climate change. This inclusive approach set the foundation for future efforts to create a balanced and effective coastal adaptation strategy across the EU.

The events also underscored the importance of reporting and collaboration in tackling local climate issues. Summary of key messages highlighted how affordable smart technologies and citizen science empower communities to work with stakeholders in developing solutions for climate resilience. Tools like low-cost sensors, digital twins, and co-creation platforms allow communities to actively engage in climate action, especially in coastal regions, leading to sustainable urban development and strengthened public participation.

Quotes from speakers further emphasized these themes:

Iulia Anton: *"Smart technologies and citizen science give communities the tools to take an active role in addressing climate challenges. With innovations like low-cost sensors and digital twins, we're not only creating solutions but empowering people to lead the way in."*

Salem Gharbia: *"The utilisation of citizen science and smart technologies within the living lab approach will empower communities to act collectively on climate change. This is one of the main concepts the SCORE project (www.score-eu-project.eu) is validating and promoting."*

Giovanni Serafino: *"Smart technologies and digital twins will change our way of conceiving urban planning, leading to a larger participation of citizens."*

APPENDIX 1: PICTURES FROM THE LITTORAL24 EVENT

APPENDIX 2: PICTURES FROM THE EUWRC EVENT

